

Biodiversity

One supported by thousands...

The largest number of species on this globe are microscopic while very few species are large – this also holds true for the Barents Sea. It takes many, and mostly small species to make the Barents Sea a healthy and productive system that can support its predators. In the Nansen Legacy, we added previously overlooked species to the inventory of living biota in this area and confirmed that known species are still present. Knowledge on the biodiversity and distribution of species in this region are an essential basis for management and conservation measures.

Number of species
at Nansen Legacy sites

ca. 150
ZOOPLANKTON

>500
SEAFLOOR SPECIES
(INVERTEBRATES)

>1500
SEA ICE
MICROBES (PROTISTS)

>2500
WATER COLUMN
MICROBES (PROTISTS)

Habitat diversity and species contributions to the ecosystem

Polar regions exhibit a unique habitat diversity, as they have sea ice as a third realm in addition to the water column and seafloor. Within each realm, microbes are the engine of our oceans and contribute most to biomass: Phytoplankton and ice algae produce the 'fuel' for the food web, and bacteria recycle other organisms' waste and move enormous amounts of energy through the marine system. Many planktonic and benthic invertebrates are prey for species used by humans such as fish and shellfish. The Arctic shelf east of Svalbard and north of the Polar Front houses communities different from the southern, Atlantic shelf, and in basin waters, species communities are totally different from either shelf community. The great diversity of organisms provides us with many services such as oxygen production, uptake of greenhouse gases, medical compounds, food, and tourist entertainment. And yet, we are losing biodiversity and sea ice as an entire habitat at an alarming rate.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The Nansen Legacy's findings provided needed information towards the newly formulated target of protecting 30% of planet earth by 2030, set at the 'United Nations Biodiversity Conference' in 2022 (COP15) meeting. The NL's study region includes Norway's last 'Arctic biodiversity area' east of Svalbard, an area worth protecting. Our data also support the goals of the Circumpolar Biodiversity Monitoring Programme of the Conservation of Arctic Flora and Fauna under the Arctic Council where we can contribute to the next update of the 'State of the Arctic Biodiversity' report. Also, our findings from the Nansen and Amundsen Basins fill knowledge gaps related to the International Agreement to prevent Unregulated Fishing in the High Seas of the Central Arctic Ocean that entered into force mid-2021.